

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable 4.3

Report on FINAL VERSION of Mission ontology and semantic network and guidance for use

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Executive Summary

Within the Prep4Blue project, Fraunhofer Austria (FhA) is leading task 4.1, which includes the development of the Mission Ocean Ecosystem (MOE) ontology as well of the semantic network for all Mission activities.

The developed ontology defines relevant concepts and their relations to the Mission's goals and objectives, such as research projects, citizen science, stakeholders, funding, and solutions. This formalisation has been used to build a semantic network from various data sources.

The final version targeting developers can be accessed using the link <https://prep4blue.ddd.fraunhofer.at:7473/browser/>.

For credentials, please contact rene.berndt@fraunhofer.at. After login the semantic network of the Mission Ocean Ecosystem can be explored using the Neo4j browser. A detailed description of how to use the Neo4j Browser can be found [HERE¹](#).

The MOE semantic network contains currently:

- 71,928 research projects
- 96,863 stakeholders
- 10,730 classification terms
- 49 engagement methods
- 37 Solutions/Knowledge output
- 2,669,909 relations between the above elements

This document replaces deliverable [D4.1 Report on INITIAL VERSION of Mission ontology and semantic network and guidance for use](#). Part 1 contains minor modifications, while Part 2 has been updated to reflect the current state. Part 3: Guidance: Using the semantic network, includes an example demonstrating the application of the semantic network in a real-life scenario, it demonstrates supporting stakeholder selection in the Pathway to Impact process.

¹ <https://neo4j.com/developer/neo4j-browser/>

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
(the) Mission	Mission Ocean and Waters
CIDOC	Comité international pour la documentation
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
CRM	Conceptual Reference Model
DB	Database
DINGO	Data INtegration for Grants Ontology
ELI	European Legislation Identifier
EURIO	EUropean Research Information Ontology
EuroSciVoc	European Science Vocabulary
EuroVoc	European Union's terminology database
FRAPO	Funding, Research Administration and Projects Ontology
KO	Knowledge Output
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MO	Mission Ocean and Waters
MOE	Mission Ocean Ecosystem
MOEOM	Mission Ocean Ecosystem Ontology Map
NACE	Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community
P4B	PREP4BLUE
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
TGN	Thesaurus of Geographic Names
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

1 Introduction

Missions are a new instrument in the Horizon Europe program, which aims to tackle societal challenges with systemic solutions. The implementation of five Missions themes (Restore our ocean and waters by 2030, Adaptation to Climate Change, Cancer, Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and Soil Health and Food) was launched in 2021.

Funded under the EU Horizon Europe program, Prep4Blue is a three-year project that sets the scene for co-creating and co-implementing the research and innovation required to achieve the objectives of the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 (hereafter “MO” or (the) Mission) by using the dedicated enablers “Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System” and “Public mobilization and engagement”.

Within Prep4Blue, WP4 (*“Knowledge Management: Identifying and Transferring Knowledge/Solutions to Support the Mission”*) as such aims to support effective knowledge management, especially in helping to identify high potential knowledge/solutions and effectively transfer them to target end-users for uptake/application in support of the Mission. The mission ontology/semantic network together with the Mission Ecosystem database (DB) will link the various aspects, actions, partners, and stakeholders to support an efficient exchange of expertise and best practices as well as explore synergies and complementarities.

The Mission Ocean ecosystem (hereafter “MOE”) consists of various domains from research over legal aspects to citizen engagement, business model etc. with its specific ontologies and vocabularies. From a knowledge perspective they can be seen as isolated or knowledge “islands”. Using ontology alignment, the MOE will connect these “islands”. Ontology alignment makes sure that two different sets of information, often represented using different categories or terms, can work together and understand each other. It's comparable to translating between two languages to ensure that even though the words might be different, the meaning behind them matches up.

In the digital world, different computer systems or databases might use their own ways to organize and describe information. Ontology alignment helps to find common ground between these different ways of organizing information. In the sense of a map that says, "This term in system A is the same as that term in system B."

For example, if one system talks about "cars" and another talks about "automobiles," ontology alignment helps us realize that these terms essentially mean the same thing, so when these systems need to work together, they understand each other's language. It's about finding connections between different ways of expressing information so that computers can share and use data more easily.

This document is divided into three parts addressing different target audiences:

- [Part 1](#) (Chapter 2 to 4) gives a short introduction of Ontologies and Semantic Networks and how they will apply to the project. The target audience for these chapters are non-technical partners and users of the MOE ontology and the semantic network.
- [Part 2](#) (Chapter 5 to 6) targets developers and gives guidelines for usage and implementing the MOE semantic network. Therefore, the language used in this section is technical and not easily understandable by those outside of developers who are the target audience.
- [Part 3](#) (Chapter 7) illustrates how the semantic network assists in identifying relevant stakeholders to improve existing solutions. This is included in the demonstration of the effective transfer of Key Exploitable Results (KER) as part of Task 4.4.

Part 1: Introduction to Ontologies and Semantic Networks

2 Ontology

This chapter introduces the fundamental concepts of ontologies and semantic networks, outlining the essential terms and ideas. Additionally, it delves into the developmental processes associated with ontologies. The focus of this chapter is on elucidating the key principles and stages involved in understanding and constructing ontologies.

2.1 Definitions

Ontology is a branch of philosophy and computer science that deals with the study of existence, categorization, and the relationships between different entities or concepts within a specific domain of knowledge. In the context of computer science and information systems, ontologies are used to represent and organize knowledge in a structured and formal manner. They define a set of concepts, their attributes, and the relationships between these concepts, providing a framework for understanding and reasoning about a particular domain. Ontologies are commonly used in fields like artificial intelligence, knowledge management, and the Semantic Web to enable machines to understand and interpret information more effectively.

A **semantic network** is a graphical representation of knowledge or information in the form of nodes (representing concepts or entities) and edges (representing relationships or links between these concepts). Semantic networks are used to model and organize structured information in a way that reflects the meaning and associations between different elements. Semantic networks can be used to represent various types of information, such as hierarchical taxonomies, concept maps, and ontologies, to facilitate the understanding and retrieval of knowledge.

To break these definitions down:

Ontology is a structured way of organizing information to help computers and people understand concepts and their relationships. They consist of the following three components:

- **Classes:** These are categories or groups that things belong to. For example, "Animals" can be a class.
- **Properties:** These are characteristics or attributes that describe classes. For instance, "hasLegs" could be a property of the class "Animals."
- **Individuals:** These are specific instances or examples of classes. If "Dog" is a class, then your pet dog, named "Buddy," is an individual.

Ontology helps to define and connect these elements. For instance, it can say that a "Dog" is a type of "Animal" and that it has the property "hasLegs" with a value of 4.

Ontologies organize information in a way that makes sense to both humans and computers. It promotes consistency in how information is stored and used, making it easier for different systems to understand and share data.

Example: Imagine a library. The classes could be "Books," "Authors," and "Genres." Properties might include "hasAuthor" and "hasGenre." The individual "Harry Potter" is a book, written by the author "J.K. Rowling," belonging to the "Fantasy" genre.

So why do we not have not a single ontology that fits all? Creating a universal ontology for the entire world is a challenging task for several reasons:

1. Diversity of Knowledge Domains:
 - The world is incredibly diverse, and knowledge spans a vast array of domains such as science, culture, technology, and more. A one-size-fits-all ontology might not adequately capture the intricacies of each specialized field.
2. Changing Knowledge:
 - Knowledge is dynamic and constantly evolving. New discoveries, technological advancements, and shifts in cultural understanding happen regularly. Maintaining a single, up-to-date ontology for the entire world would be practically impossible.
3. Interdisciplinary Nature:
 - Many fields overlap, and interdisciplinary work is common. A rigid, universal ontology might struggle to accommodate the nuanced relationships between different domains.
4. Cultural and Linguistic Variations:
 - Different cultures and languages have unique ways of expressing and categorizing concepts. A global ontology might not appropriately represent the diversity of cultural perspectives and linguistic nuances.
5. Context Dependence:
 - The meaning of terms and concepts often depends on the context in which they are used. A global ontology might oversimplify or misrepresent concepts by ignoring context-specific meanings.
6. Privacy and Security Concerns:
 - A universal ontology would need to handle sensitive information. Managing and securing such a system on a global scale raises significant privacy and security concerns.
7. Governance and Control:
 - Determining who gets to define and control a global ontology raises governance issues. Different communities may have conflicting interests and perspectives on how concepts should be represented.

Instead of a single, world ontology, the approach often taken is to develop domain-specific ontologies tailored to particular fields or applications. These smaller ontologies can then be linked or integrated as needed, allowing for more flexibility and adaptability in representing diverse knowledge. The idea is to build interoperability between ontologies rather than imposing a singular, overarching structure.

The following section gives an overview of the workflow for designing a domain-specific ontology.

2.2 Development Workflow

Figure 1 Ontology Development Workflow

Following the workflow (see Figure 1) for developing an ontology the following actions have been carried out respectively and/or are ongoing:

1. Define the Domain and Purpose/Consider reuse:

In this context, the ontology's specific domain or subject of focus is determined. For the project PREP4BLUE the domain is the so-called Mission Ocean Ecosystem (MOE). Chapter 3 gives an overview of the related domain belonging to the MOE as well as their top-level concepts.

2. Identify External Sources:

In addition to defining the ontology, particularly outlining its concepts and their interconnections, a crucial step involves identifying the external sources you intend to incorporate into your ontology, which may encompass research initiatives, funding prospects, databases, and related references.

The main source will be the MOE database (Task 4.1), which serves as the ground truth.

3. Select an Ontology Language:

With all the different domains which contribute to the MOE, The *Comité international pour la documentation Conceptual Reference Model* (in short CIDOC-CRM) has been chosen as a guidance for creating the MOE ontology. It has been proven to be a theoretical and practical tool for information integration in the field of cultural heritage.

Chapter 4 gives a short overview of this conceptual reference model.

4. Define Core Concepts, Classes, Relationships:

Key classes of the MO ecosystem are defined based on core classes on CIDOC-CRM. Chapter 5 gives a short overview on how concepts of MOE are expressed as an extension to the existing representation. While preserving the open world assumption, this approach makes it easier to integrate additional data sources with their corresponding metadata schemes.

5. Create Instances:

Based on a graph database (neo4j²) a set of tools using the Python programming language has been developed to map existing data into instances of the MOE ontology, which serve as examples/guidelines of how to integrate data into the semantic network.

- Create projects from MOE database
- Create projects, results from CORDIS data
- Create controlled vocabulary (NACE, EuroSciVoc, EuroVoc, TRL)
- Create relations between projects, results, and controlled vocabulary.

6. Document and Annotate:

The MOE will follow the documentation style and guidelines from CIDOC-CRM.

Chapter 6 contains the programming and usage guidance for the ontology and the semantic network. These guidelines mainly address developer and maintainer of the MOE database and the mission dashboard.

The next chapter Mission Ocean Ecosystem gives an overview of the current state for *step 1* (define the Domain and Purpose/Consider reuse) and *step 2* (Identify External Sources) in the ontology development workflow. It defines the domain and gives a reference for considered ontologies, vocabulary/thesauri and data sources.

² <https://neo4j.com/>

Centered around the Mission Ocean with its objectives and actions, there are five key areas contributing to the Mission Ocean ecosystem:

- RESEARCH
 - Projects and their direct results (publication, patents, etc.)
 - Extracted Knowledge Output according to Task 4.3.
- BUSINESS
 - Financial ecosystem including funding, business model, etc.
- ACTORS
 - Stakeholders and Citizens including the various methodologies for engagement
- LEGAL
 - Legal domain (EU regulations, directives, local laws, etc.)
- MARITIME
 - Marine domain (Digital twin of the ocean, WoRMS, etc.)

In this first version for the MOE ontology the focus was on the research and the actor domain aligned with the data stored MOE database.

For each of the five key areas outlined above, relevant ontologies, vocabularies/thesauri, and data sources are listed. These resources contribute either as support for design decisions or for enriching the data within the MOE database.

3.1 Actors Domain

3.1.1 Ontologies

FOAF

FOAF stands for "Friend of a Friend." It is an ontology and a set of conventions for creating machine-readable representations of people, their activities, and their relationships.

CIDOC-CRM institution information

Since the MOE ontology is based on CIDOC-CRM the default mechanism for defining actors (in particular E39-Actor and E74-Group) will be used for stakeholders and citizens. Figure 3 shows the default pattern of how to model institution information.

3.1.2 Vocabularies/Thesauri

NACE

NACE, or the Nomenclature of Economic Activities, is the European standard classification system for productive economic activities. It partitions the universe of economic activities into distinct codes, which can be assigned to statistical units performing these activities. This classification facilitates the collection, analysis, and dissemination of economic data across out [[CE08](#)].

3.2.3 Source

MOEDB and CORDIS data predominantly represent research institutions, such as universities. They do not provide a comprehensive list of commercial entities. It would be advantageous to incorporate data from the Business Registers of EU countries to include these entities.

3.3 Research Domain

3.3.1 Ontologies

European Research Information Ontology (EURIO)

EURIO has been developed by CORDIS on the basis of data about research projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for research and innovation following Semantic Web standards. EURIO is aligned with EU ontologies such as DINGO and FRAPO and de facto standard ontologies such as schema.org and the Organization Ontology from W3C. Moreover, it models projects and actors such as people and organizations, while also including administrative information like funding schemes and grants.

Data Integration and Extension for Grant Ontology (DINGO)

DINGO, the Data Integration and Extension for Grant Ontology, is an ontology expressly designed to provide an extensible interoperable framework for formally conceptualizing and expressing the relevant parts of the research/cultural landscape in relation to funding, such that they can easily be shared between different actors and platforms.

3.3.2 Vocabularies/Thesauri

EuroSciVoc

EuroSciVoc is a multilingual taxonomy that represents all the main fields of science that were discovered from CORDIS content and organised through a semiautomatic process based on NLP techniques. It contains more than 1000 categories in 6 languages (English, French, German, Italian, Polish and Spanish) and each category is enriched with relevant keywords extracted from the textual description of CORDIS projects. It is specifically developed as a reference vocabulary for the Open Science community and is aligned with Linked Open Data standards.

3.3.3 Sources

EU funding programmes

EU funding programmes as well as funded projects can be retrieved using the "Community Research and Development Information Service" (CORDIS). It is the European Union's (EU) primary online portal for information related to EU-funded research and innovation programs. CORDIS is managed by the European Commission and provides access to a wide range of information about EU-funded projects, research initiatives, and innovation activities. For the MOE ontology it is one of the main data sources.

National funding programs of the EU member states

In addition to EU-level research funding, it's important to note that there are also national research funding opportunities available within the European Union member states, like the *Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft* (DFG) as the central self-governing organization for academic research in Germany.

3.4 Legal Domain

3.4.1 Ontologies

European Legislation Identifier (ELI)

The European Legislation Identifier (ELI) is a framework to make legislation metadata available online in a standardised format, so that it can be accessed, exchanged and reused across borders[[otE](#)].

3.4.2 Vocabularies/Thesauri

EuroVoc

EuroVoc is a multilingual, multidisciplinary thesaurus developed and maintained by the Publications Office of the European Union. It is a standardized vocabulary that serves as a tool for indexing, categorizing, and retrieving documents and information related to the European Union (EU) and its institutions. EuroVoc is used primarily for the classification and retrieval of documents within the EU's various language versions, making it easier to access and understand EU-related content in multiple languages. EuroVoc is used in ELI as a standardized and multilingual thesaurus that helps classify, index, and categorize legal documents within the EU.

3.4.3 Source

EURLex is an online service that provides access to European Union law, including treaties, legislation, case law, and legislative proposals. It offers extensive search functionalities and multilingual support to facilitate the retrieval of legal documents. EURLex is an essential tool for legal professionals, researchers, and anyone interested in EU law and its legislative processes.

3.5 Maritime Domain

3.5.1 Ontologies

No ontologies for the maritime domain have been included in the MOE ontology.

3.5.2 Vocabularies/Thesauri

World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS)

The "World Register of Marine Species" (WoRMS) is an online database that aims to provide a comprehensive and authoritative list of all known marine species in the world. It is a global initiative led by the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ) in Belgium, and it involves collaboration with a vast network of marine scientists and taxonomists from around the world. The primary goal of WoRMS is to create a standardized and up-to-date taxonomic and nomenclatural reference for marine species (see Figure 4).

WoRMS taxon details

★ ***Sphyrna zygaena* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

AphiaID	105819 (urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:tax-name:105819)	<p>© Andy Murray@iawmshar.com</p> <p>★ To FishBase images ...</p>
Classification	Biota > ★ <i>Animalia</i> (Kingdom)	
	> ★ <i>Chordata</i> (Phylum)	
	> ★ <i>Vertebrata</i> (Subphylum)	
	> ☆ <i>Gnathostomata</i> (Infraphylum)	
	> ★ <i>Chondrichthyes</i> (Parvphylum)	
	> ★ <i>Elasmobranchii</i> (Class)	
	> ★ <i>Neoselachii</i> (Subclass)	
	> ★ <i>Selachii</i> (Infraclass)	
	> ☆ <i>Galeomorphi</i> (Superorder)	
	> ★ <i>Carcharhiniformes</i> (Order)	
	> ★ <i>Sphyrnidae</i> (Family)	
	> ★ <i>Sphyrna</i> (Genus)	
	> ★ <i>Sphyrna zygaena</i> (Species)	
Status	accepted	
Rank	Species	
Typetaxon of	★ <i>Sphyrna Rafinesque, 1810</i>	
Parent	★ <i>Sphyrna Rafinesque, 1810</i>	
Orig. name	★ <i>Squalus zygaena</i> Linnaeus, 1758	

Figure 4 WoRMS webpage for hammerhead shark.

3.5.3 Sources

Linking to the maritime domain, whether by species (WoRMS) or location (Getty TGN), is initiated by textual descriptions of companies, research projects, or solutions.

3.6 Cross Cutting Principles

This section lists cross-cutting principles, which are not clearly belonging to one of the five key areas above, e.g. the Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (Getty TGN or short TGN) can be for defining the location of stakeholders as well as location to which research projects contribute.

3.6.1 Vocabularies/Thesauri

Technical Readiness level

Technical Readiness Level (TRL) is a concept used in various industries, particularly in engineering, aerospace, and technology, to assess the maturity and readiness of a technology or innovation for practical application. It provides a standardized way to measure the progress of a technology from the early research stages to its readiness for commercialization and deployment. TRL levels are defined with specific criteria, making it a valuable tool for decision-making, funding allocation, and project management.

The nine TRL levels as defined in the "HORIZON 2020 – WORK PROGRAMME 2014-2015 General Annexes" are:

- TRL 1 – basic principles observed
- TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
- TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
- TRL 4 – technology validated in lab
- TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
- TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
- TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN)

The Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN) is a structured vocabulary and database that provides information about places, including geographical names, historical names, and other related data. It is maintained and published by the Getty Research Institute, a part of the J. Paul Getty Trust, which is known for its involvement in art research and cultural heritage.

The TGN helps standardize and control the use of geographic names to ensure consistency in cataloguing and documentation. Figure 5 shows the webpage which resolves TGN id 1000003 to Europe.

Click the icon to view the hierarchy.

[Semantic View \(JSON, JSONLD, RDF, N3/Turtle, N-Triples\)](#)

ID: 1000003 **Record Type:** [physical](#)

Page Link: <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/tgn/1000003>

 Europe (continent)

Coordinates:
 Lat: 56 12 00 N *degrees minutes* Lat: 56.2000 *decimal degrees*
 Long: 015 01 00 E *degrees minutes* Long: 15.0160 *decimal degrees*

Note: Europe was an early home to Homo erectus, Neanderthal and modern Homo sapiens. Agricultural settlements arose in the 7th millennium BCE. Advanced civilizations developed here in the Mediterranean area with Asian and African influences. Modern European nations began to form after the fall of the Western Roman Empire in the fifth century CE. The late 20th and early 21st centuries have witnessed the formation and expansion of the European Union, a group of European nations allied for trade and some administrative purposes, such as a common currency.

Names:
 Europe ([preferred,C,O,English-P,U,N](#))
 (French)
 Europa ([C,O,Swedish](#))
 (Basque)
 (Catalan)
 (Spanish)
 (Norwegian)
 (Romanian)
 (Portuguese)
 (Polish)

Figure 5. TGN Example for the place Europe.

4 CIDOC CRM

The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM)³ is a theoretical and practical tool for information integration in the field of cultural heritage. It can help researchers, administrators and the public explore complex questions with regards to our past across diverse and dispersed datasets. The CIDOC CRM achieves this by providing definitions and a formal structure for describing the implicit and explicit concepts and relationships used in cultural heritage documentation and of general interest for the querying and exploration of such data. Such models are also known as formal ontologies. These formal descriptions allow the integration of data from multiple sources in a software and schema agnostic fashion [BBD+21]. Schema-agnostic in this context means that data from different sources needs to be aligned, because for example the data format for research projects provided by CORDIS is different from the format provided by UN Decade.

The CIDOC CRM has been developed in a manner that is intended to promote a shared understanding of cultural heritage information by providing a common and extensible semantic framework for evidence-based cultural heritage information integration. It is intended to be a common language for domain experts and implementers to formulate requirements for information systems and to serve as a guide for good practice of conceptual modelling. In this way, it can provide the "semantic glue" needed to mediate between different sources of cultural heritage information, such as that published by museums, libraries and archives.

The CIDOC CRM is the outcome of over 20 years of development and maintenance work, originally by the CIDOC Documentation Standards Working Group and, presently, by the CIDOC CRM SIG, both of which are working groups of CIDOC. Since December, 2006, it has been recognized as an official ISO standard. This status was renewed in 2014 and can be found at [ISO 21127:2014](https://www.iso.org/standard/62266.html). The CIDOC CRM is a living standard that is designed in such a way as to provide both high level information retrieval and the formulation and documentation of very specific data points and questions. The CIDOC CRM thus consists of the CRMbase standard which provides the basic classes and relations devised for the cultural heritage world.

This CRMbase (base ontology) is complemented by a series of modular extensions to the basic model. Such extensions are designed to support different types of specialized research questions and documentation such as bibliographic documentation or geoinformatics. The CIDOC CRM extensions are developed in partnership with the research communities in question. These extensions are formulated in a manner that is harmonized with the base ontology such that data expressed in any extension is compatible with the base system of concepts and relations. This harmonized development process leads to a high level of information integrity and integration not available in other information systems.

³ CIDOC CRM V7.1.1 <https://doi.org/10.26225/FDZH-X261>

The base concepts and their typical connection/interaction between them are highlighted in Figure 6:

1. E55 Type:
 - *Definition:* E55 Type is a class representing a category or class of entities. It is used to classify entities into specific types or categories.
 - *Example:* If you have an entity representing a painting, its E55 Type might be "Oil Painting" or "Watercolor."
2. E41 Appellation:
 - *Definition:* E41 Appellation represents the assignment of a name or label to an entity. It is used to capture different names or titles associated with an entity.
 - *Example:* If you have an entity representing a person, the E41 Appellation might include different names or titles that person is known by.
3. E39 Actors:
 - *Definition:* E39 Actors represent individuals or corporate bodies that play a role in events or activities. It includes both human and non-human agents.
 - *Example:* A person (human) attending an exhibition or a software agent (non-human) updating a database.
4. E2 Temporal Entities:
 - *Definition:* E2 Temporal Entities represent periods or instances in time. It is used to model temporal aspects of entities, events, and activities.
 - *Example:* A specific date (instance) or a time span (period) associated with the creation of a cultural artifact.
5. E28 Conceptual Objects:
 - *Definition:* E28 Conceptual Objects represent abstract or conceptual entities that are not physical. They are used to model ideas, concepts, or intellectual creations.
 - *Example:* The concept of "justice" or an abstract idea represented in a philosophical text.
6. E18 Physical Thing:
 - *Definition:* E18 Physical Thing represents tangible, physical entities. It is a superclass for all entities that have a material existence.
 - *Example:* A sculpture, a book, or any object that has a physical form.
7. E53 Places:
 - *Definition:* E53 Places represent locations or spaces. It is used to model places or areas associated with events, objects, or actors.
 - *Example:* The Louvre Museum (as a place) where a painting (as an object) is exhibited, or the birthplace of an individual.

These concepts are foundational elements in the CIDOC CRM and are used to model various aspects of cultural heritage information, providing a standardized way to describe entities, events, and their relationships. Figure 7 shows these foundational elements and their available refinements.

CIDOC-CRM has already been used in the maritime domain as part of the SeaLiT⁴ project as an extension for the modelling of Maritime History Information. Figure 8 displays the newly introduced SeaLiT concepts with the blue boxes.

Figure 6 Base classes of CIDOC CRM.

⁴ Seafaring Lives in Transition, Mediterranean Maritime Labour and Shipping

Figure 7 CIDOC-CRM class hierarchy.

Part 2: Developer Guidance

5 Mission Ocean Ecosystem (MOE) Ontology

This chapter gives an overview of the specific concepts by which CIDOC-CRM has been extended. The extension includes defining central elements such as missions and their objectives. An introduction into ontologies in general and into the CIDOC-CRM can be found in deliverable *D4.1 “Report on INITIAL VERSION of Mission ontology and semantic network and guidance for use”*.

5.1 Notation

To extend CIDOC CRM, new concepts are introduced with distinct notations to differentiate them from the original CIDOC CRM concepts.

Within the CIDOC CRM, entities are designated with specific prefixes to indicate their types and roles within the framework. The prefix "E" signifies entities, which are the fundamental classes representing tangible and intangible things, such as physical objects, events, and concepts. For example, E22-Man-Made-Object or E4-Period are entities within the model.

On the other hand, the prefix "P" is used for properties, which define the relationships between these entities. Properties describe how entities interact, relate, or are associated with one another. An instance of this would be P52-has-current-owner, linking an E22-Man-Made-Object to an E39-Actor representing its owner.

New entities which have introduced to the ontology are prefixed with "B" (short for “Blue”) for classes and "BP" for properties, as well as “D” for classes from DINGO followed by a unique number (e.g., B1-Mission, D1-Funding-Agency).

Figure 9 Notation for the concept's diagrams.

Figure 9 shows the notation used in this document. The top left displays a concept instance, with the concept class on the top line and instance data on the second line (e.g., an E53 Place with the TGN number for central Europe (4003755)). To illustrate the distinction between core CIDOC CRM concepts and new P4B concepts, diagrams are utilized where core CIDOC CRM concepts are depicted with a green background (top right column) and P4B concepts with blue backgrounds. The left bottom section

demonstrates the connection between two concepts using a single line property. In the right bottom section, it is indicated that an MOE entity has a CIDOC-CRM entity as its base class.

5.2 Concepts

5.2.1 Mission

The central element of the MOE ontology are the concepts of a mission and their objectives (see Figure 10). Missions are represented by **B1-Mission**, and their objectives by **B3-Mission Objective**, which are linked using properties like **P148-has-component**. This hierarchical structure allows for the incorporation of additional objectives or components, creating a comprehensive framework for organizing and managing mission-related data.

A Mission objective can have other Mission Objectives as their subcomponent or refer to another objective (*e.g.* from a different mission (see Figure 10 or an example).

The class **B7 Mission Target** comprises targets of Mission objectives, which quantifies the conditions to archive the Mission objective.

Figure 10 Mission and Mission Objectives of MOE.

Figure 11: Mission Ocean and Waters and the UN Mission Ocean Decade with their objectives.

In the semantic network, the Mission Ocean and Waters (MO) and the UN (Mission) 'Ocean Decade' have been established. Figure 11 illustrates the two missions (yellow) along with their corresponding mission objectives (red). Additionally, for MO objectives, the targets have been included (blue). The green nodes display their relationships to economic activities using the "Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community" (NACE).

5.2.2 Project

The **B2-Project** represents a (funded) research project, which exposes the characteristic of an **E7-Activity** as an activity over time as well as a **E89-PropositionalObject** that are "about" something in the sense of an research topic or idea (see Figure 12). Using **P67-refers-to** it can be connected to a MOE location (e.g. the North sea).

Connecting Actors

B1-Mission as a subclass of **E7-Activity** connects to an actor who actively participates in the project using the **P14-carried-out-by** attribute. Actor can either be an instance of an individual person (**E21-Person**) or an organisation (**E74-Group**) (e.g. a University, Interest Group, etc.).

Figure 12 A project within the MOE.

Timeline

The chronological order of a project is archived by connecting the **E52-Time-Span** using the **P4-has-time-span** attribute of **E7-Activity**, which is inherited based on the subclass relationship to **B2-Project**. A follow-up mission can be expressed using **P134-continued**. Mission (sub missions) segments can be modelled using the **P10-falls-within** attribute. Figure 13 expresses that the PREP4BLUE mission lasts from 2022 to 2025 and was continued by the PREPBLUE NG project. In addition, mission PREP4BLUE consists of the two (sub)missions PREP4BLUE WP1 and PREP4BLUE WP2.

Figure 13 Timespan and chronological order of projects (Prep4Blue project as an example).

Publications

Project outputs (e.g., publications or other deliverables) are added using the standard information model for integrating DC metadata. They are connected to the project using a **E65-Creation**, which also connects the authors **E39-Actor** as outlined in Figure 14.

Figure 14 Example of a mission with (actively) involved persons and organisations.

5.2.3 Knowledge Output/Solutions

As defined in WP4 Knowledge Output (KO) is defined as follows:

This class comprises a unit of knowledge or learning generated by or through research activity. They are not limited to de-novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know how/ knowledge.

A Knowledge Output is not: A theory, hypothesis or idea. Potential results or outputs. A Scientific publication, deliverables or report but these may contain one or multiples KOs.

Figure 15 Knowledge Output

Figure 15 shows the definition of **B4-Knowledge Output** which can refer to a mission objective. Attached KPI to the KO (like TRL, SDG, etc.) are attached as instances of **E55-Type**.

5.2.4 Engagement methods

The class **B5 Engagement Method** comprises methods of citizen/stakeholder engagement. As a method it exposes characteristic of **E29-Design-or-Procedure**. The engagement method is connected to a project by **P33-used-specific-technique** (see Figure 16).

Figure 16 Attached engagement methods to a project.

5.2.5 Mission Lighthouse

The class **B6 Mission Lighthouse** comprises sites to pilot, demonstrate, develop and deploy the Mission activities across EU seas and river basins.

Figure 17: Mission Lighthouse "Danube River"

In the semantic network this concept can be linked to projects as well as using geographics relations. Figure 17 shows the Lighthouse "Danube River" which is about the Danube River (TGN:7012913) flowing through Germany and Austria.

5.2.6 Engagement methods

The class **B5 Engagement Method** comprises methods of citizen/stakeholder engagement. As a method it exposes characteristic of **E29-Design-or-Procedure**. The engagement method is connected to a project by **P33-used-specific-technique** (see Figure 16).

5.2.7 Engagement

The class **B8 Engagement** represents various kinds of pledges like citizen science projects. Figure 18 shows the citizen science project "French Standing Network" with the related EuroVoc terms.

Figure 18: Citizen science pledge "French Stranding Network".

5.2.8 Funding and Grants

The European Research Information Ontology (EURIO) (Figure 19) conceptualises, formally encodes and makes available in an open, structured and machine-readable format data about research projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for research and innovation.

EURIO (Figure 19) has been developed by CORDIS on the basis of data about research projects funded by the EU's framework programs for research and innovation following Semantic Web standards. EURIO is aligned with EU ontologies such as DINGO and FRAPO and de facto standard ontologies such as schema.org and the Organization Ontology from W3C. Moreover, it models projects and actors such as people and organizations, while also including administrative information like funding schemes and grants.

The MOE ontology has been extended by three classes and relations from EURIO:

- **D1 Funding Agency** is the class for funding agencies: organizations that materially disburse and administer the Grant process. (<https://dcodings.github.io/DINGO/#FundingAgency>)
- **D2 Funding Scheme** is the class for funding schemes: plans, designs, and/or programs that determines and organizes the funding. (<https://dcodings.github.io/DINGO/#FundingScheme>)
- **D3 Grant** is the class for grant: a disbursed fund paid to a recipient or beneficiary and the process for it. (<https://dcodings.github.io/DINGO/#Grant>)
- **DP1_funds** defines the relation between the Grant (subject) and the Project (object).
- **DP2_implementation_of** defines the relationship between the decision, plan, program (subject) and the grant (object) that the grant is the concrete realization of.
- **DP3_implements** defines the relationship between the funding scheme and the funding agency.

Figure 20: Example of a project with grant and funding information.

Figure 20 shows the usage of the funding related classes within the MOE ontology. In this example the research project “[ToDrinQ] TOolkit for aDaptable, Resilient INstallations securing high Quality drinking

water“ has been funded by Grant “ HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01” of the HORIZON-Europe program of the European Commission.

6 Usage Guidance: Managing the semantic network

This chapter provides guidance and best practices for incorporating new data sources into semantic networks.

6.1 Handling Ids

When importing data from different data-sources, one problem is how to deal with local identifiers, because the same concept can be addressed with *id A* in one data-source and with *id B* in a second data-source. For example, a stakeholder is addressed within the CORDIS database using the id '999979500' and within the Mission Ocean Ecosystem database using the id 42. Following the *General Mapping Principles & Approach*⁵ for CIDOC-CRM:

We map local identifiers in relational database tables explicitly only if these identifiers are visible in the user interface and used in other documents as well. Alternatively, we use the local database identifiers only for generating URIs for the record instance, if the thing identified belongs to our holdings or was created/invented by us. Otherwise, we better use a global authority.

Here it is advised to use the VAT number as a global authority, but also the various local identifiers are added to the semantic network in order to identify them by local identifiers. Figure 21 shows the usage of these identifiers within the MOE ontology. The Company “CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE” as a **E74Group** is linked to the various identifiers using **P48 (has preferred identifier)**, here to the VAT number IT02118311006, the local CORDIS identifier 999979500 and the local identifier for the MOE database 42.

Using a prefix describing the ID of the instance of **E42Identifier** helps to distinct the various numbers using the source and optional the type:

- VAT:<vat_number> for addressing an organization using their VAT number
- CORDIS:Org: <local_cordis_id> for addressing organizations within the CORDIS
- MOEDB:Org:<local_moedb_id> for addressing organizations within the MOE database

⁵ <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/Resources/methodological-tips-for-mappings-to-cidoc-crm>

Figure 21: Stakeholder with various local ids.

6.2 Mapping Guideline

Although CIDOC CRM is rooted in cultural heritage and can manage sparse data, the quality of the data significantly impacts its effectiveness for performing the required tasks.

- If a new data source is connected to the semantic network, it might be necessary to define a new MO concept, but when a new class is needed? The creation of new classes and relations should follow the “Minimality” modelling principle of CIDOC CRM: *“A class is not declared unless it is required as the domain or range of a property not appropriate to its superclass, or it is a key concept in the practical scope”*

Figure 22: Connecting a project to a source (E31Document) using P70i_is_documented_in.

6.3 Programming Guide

6.3.1 Python Library

The Python library for creating the semantic network has been refactored following the principles of a fluent interface, which is an object-oriented API whose design relies extensively on method chaining. Its goal is to increase code legibility by creating a domain-specific language.

Figure 24: Mission Ocean and their objectives as created from the code example.

The following code snippet shows the fluent API in action when creating the Mission/MissionObjective structure as shown in Figure 24:

```
m = p4b.Mission("MissionBlue", "EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters 2030'", url="https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programme
.add_objective(value="MO 1 (Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity)", uid="MissionBlue_01") \
.add_objective(value="MO 2 (Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters)", uid="MissionBlue_02") \
.add_objective(value="MO 3 (Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular)", uid="MissionBlue_03") \
```

The library provides examples for importing and mapping data from CORDIS, MOE database for research projects, citizen science, places, stakeholders, vocabularies (NACE, TRL, EuroSciVoc, EuroVoc).

6.3.2 Visualization

Semantic networks are an essential tool for representing structured information in various domains, from linguistics to artificial intelligence. Visualizing these networks effectively is crucial for understanding complex relationships and gaining insights from data.

For a web-based visualization the script **show_graph_from_cypher.py** can be used. It uses the PyVis library (<https://pyvis.readthedocs.io/en/latest/#>) to create an interactive visualization for a given cypher query. Figure 25 shows the interactive visualization for the following query:

```
MATCH (:E42Identifier{uid:'862658_KOg'})<--(:B4KnowledgeOutput)-->(t:E55Type) WITH COLLECT(t.uid) as UIDS
MATCH (:E42Identifier{uid:'862658_KOg'})<--(:B4KnowledgeOutput)-->(t:E55Type)<--(p:B2Project) where t.uid in UIDS
with count(t) as CNT, p as RESULT
WHERE CNT>4
UNWIND RESULT as pp
MATCH ppp=( :E42Identifier{uid:'862658_KOg'})<--(:B4KnowledgeOutput)-->(t:E55Type)<--(tp:B2Project) where tp.uid = pp.uid
return ppp
```


Figure 25: PyVis graph for a cypher query.

Several software libraries exist to aid in the visualization of semantic networks, each offering unique features and capabilities.

6.3.2.1 PyVis

PyVis is a popular Python library designed for creating interactive network visualizations. It leverages the power of the JavaScript library Vis.js, allowing users to generate and customize network graphs with ease. PyVis is particularly well-suited for visualizing semantic networks due to its flexibility and extensive range of features. Key Features are:

- Interactive visualizations with zooming, panning, and node dragging capabilities.
- Customizable node and edge properties, including colors, sizes, and labels.
- Integration with NetworkX for seamless graph creation and manipulation.
- Export options for saving visualizations as HTML files for easy sharing and embedding.

6.3.2.2 *NetworkX*

NetworkX is a comprehensive Python library for the creation, manipulation, and study of complex networks. While it primarily focuses on graph analysis, it also provides basic visualization capabilities that can be enhanced with other libraries like Matplotlib and PyVis. Key Features are:

- Support for various graph types, including directed, undirected, and multigraphs.
- A wide range of algorithms for network analysis, including shortest path, clustering, and centrality measures.
- Integration with visualization libraries like Matplotlib and PyVis for enhanced visual representations.
- Ability to handle large-scale networks efficiently.

6.3.2.3 *Graphviz*

Graphviz is an open-source graph visualization software that provides a simple yet powerful way to visualize semantic networks. It uses the DOT language to describe graphs and generate visual representations in various formats. Key Features are:

- Support for multiple output formats, including PNG, PDF, and SVG.
- Ability to create complex layouts with minimal effort using the DOT language.
- Integration with Python through libraries like PyGraphviz and Pydot.
- Customizable node and edge styles to enhance the visual appeal of graphs.

6.3.3 *Utilities*

In order to build the semantic network, the following utilities have been developed to support the creation process.

6.3.3.1 *Caching*

When you have a large amount of data which needs to be processed like a large Excel-Table, caching can be useful.

If the result of the processing is always the same and the processing needs a lot of time, you do the processing once and save the results in a file. Later on you only need to do the processing again if the source data changes.

In different parts of our program caching is used. In the TGN resolver for example and in the EuroVocClassifier caching is used. The loading of data in the database also makes use of caching in general.

6.3.3.2 *TGN Resolver*

The Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN) is a structured vocabulary of geographic names. The TGN resolver takes the descriptions of projects and uses them to match the projects to corresponding TGNs. So there are connections between projects and relevant areas for example where this project was realized.

The TGN resolver is realized in different steps where each step uses the result of the previous. First Named Entity Recognition (NER) is used to extract interesting names of locations out of the project description.

The next step maps the names of locations to real location names using fuzzy search. In the last step for the real location names the corresponding TGNs are queried.

NER is used to recognize different entities in sentences. For example, you can have the following sentence:

The deep Dead Sea temperature is mainly influenced by winter air temperature and its level depends on the Jordan discharge that is fueled by winter rainfall.

If you try NER on this example, it will mark the following words with tags:

- Dead Sea LOC
- winter DATE
- Jordan GPE
- winter DATE

The tags in the example have this meaning:

- GPE - Countries, cities, states
- LOC - Non-GPE locations, mountain ranges, bodies of water
- DATE - Absolute or relative dates or periods

In our framework we only process string marked with LOC or GPE.

We then use a list of locations and their TGN. We match this list with the words found in the last step using fuzzy search. Fuzzy search marks two words as identical if they are identical or differ only in subtle details. This can be one letter for example.

One problem can arise if a term has more than one TGN associated. If you look at the term "Dead Sea" above it has more than one places to choose (see Figure 26).

 Dead Sea (sea)

Coordinates:
 Lat: 39 58 24 S *degrees minutes* Lat: -39.9733 *decimal degrees*
 Long: 143 56 26 E *degrees minutes* Long: 143.9405 *decimal degrees*

Names:
 Dead Sea ([preferred,C,V,English,U](#))

Hierarchical Position:

- [World](#) (facet)
- [Oceania](#) (continent) (P)
- [Australia](#) (nation) (P)
- [State of Tasmania](#) (state) (P)
- [Dead Sea](#) (sea) (P,U)

Figure 26: TGN entry for the Dead Sea.

Also, if you look at Jordan there are many alternatives to choose from (see Figure 27).

Figure 27: TGN entry for the Jordan.

One must take one of the alternatives using a heuristic. At the end we have projects and a list of TGNs for each project.

The TGN Resolver searches for ocean names or nation names in project descriptions and saves the project_id and tgn to a file. It does this in several steps using different python scripts.

First the script tgn/spacy_recog.py is used. The main() function loads the project objectives using ld_objectives(). Then recog() is used to recognize entities of type `LOC` or `GPE` and writes a csv containing `project_id, start, end, text, label`. For this recognition Spacy is used, which can detect entity types described in <https://www.kaggle.com/code/curiousprogrammer/entity-extraction-and-classification-using-spacy>.

Then the `main()` function in `tgn/test_recog_tgn.py` must be called. It loads extracted names from file and saves them unique to a file. It queries all ocean and nation names from the getty database and saves them to two files.

At last the `main()` in `tgn/test_fuzz_match.py` generates a mapping between keywords and projects. It saves the project_id, the name of the ocean or country and the TGN to files. For this it uses find_places_tgns() where first get_kw_project_id() is called. This function returns a list of tuples with (text,project_id) where each text is the name of an entity. Then the function search_simil_places() searches a possible place for each keyword and returns a dict of found keywords and the found place. Then the function get_TGNs_for_places() returns the tgn for each found place. At last the project_ids and TGNs are mapped.

6.3.3.1 *EuroVoc Classifier*

The `MLUtils.py` contains the function `classify_EuroVoc()` which classifies text to EuroVoc ids. The `init_EuroVoc()` is used to initialize the tool. It uses a machine learning model to classify the text.

The `classify_EuroVoc()` function is used in `class_projects.py`. In this library the objective of each CORDIS-project is classified using `classify_EuroVoc()`. The output is saved to a cache file.

The `classify_EuroVoc()` function is also used in `class_mates.py`. There it is used to classify the description of the project partners.

Part 3: Guidance: Using the semantic network

7 Using the semantic network for the KER Impact pathways

This chapter provides an example of how the MOE semantic network can be utilized to perform specific tasks. In this instance, it supports the **Pathway to Impact** by identifying relevant target users for a transfer activity for a Key Exploitable Result (KER) as described in [D4.2: Customized Knowledge Management Method for Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters](#).

The purpose of the **Pathway to Impact** is to outline the steps necessary to transition a **Knowledge Output** from its current state to its ultimate application, generating measurable impact. It maps the stakeholders, actions, and resources required at each stage, ensuring that the output aligns with mission objectives and delivers tangible benefits to society, the environment, or the economy (Figure 28).

Figure 28: Pathway to impact from knowledge output to impact.

As part of *Task 4.3 (Collect and Analyse Mission Knowledge/Solutions)*, descriptions of knowledge generated by EU funded projects were identified and those with a high possibility to respond to the MO objectives were described in standardized templates as Key Exploitable Results (KER).

One of these KERs was titled "*Precision model to map chlorophyll-a concentration in shallow water for the shellfish aquaculture industry*". The description of this KO was used in the example below to show how information can be gathered from the ontology and semantic network to inform the mapping of a pathway to impact. Figure 29 show the textual information presented in Wavelinks (<https://wavelinks.eu>).

Precision model to map chlorophyll-a concentration in shallow water for the shellfish aqu... Prep4Blue

Background Description: The estimation of chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentration in coastal waters still has some difficulties in comparison to oceanic waters due to the more complex optical properties and to the high spatial variability of the coastal environment. Atmospheric and scale corrections are necessary to remotely and accurately estimate Chl-a concentration in coastal waters, which is of main importance to evaluate the viability (based on the environmental status of water masses) of integrating bivalve (i.e., mussel) aquaculture systems in marine spatial plans; the objective of these carrying capacity...

Technical Description: A shellfish farm may exceed the ecological carrying capacity when the removal of phytoplankton biomass exceeds the renewal, resulting in a phytoplankton depleted water mass. To comply with the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) on bivalve aquaculture standards, the renewal time of each area has to be shorter than the clearance rate time. Thus, NewTechAqua, through a series of sampling cruises (n = 17) for over a year (September 2020 to October 2021) in the northern (n = 9) and southern (n = 8) embayment of the Ebro Delta (eastern Iberian Peninsula), developed a highly innovative...

Potential Impact And Applications: This KO is now at MRR1 for the Delta del Ebro estuary as case study. This methodology shows the potential of the combined use of satellite remote sensing, in situ sampling, and carrying capacity models as a tool for helping the low trophic aquaculture industry to expand their activities to new suitable areas and, therefore, closely linked to Mission Objective 3, target 1: "Develop zero-carbon and low-impact aquaculture, and promote circular, low-carbon multi-purpose use of marine and water space". The methodology used help policy-makers on the decision making process by providing...

Title: Precision model to map chlorophyll-a concentration in shallow water for the shellfish aquaculture industry.

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Figure 29: Wavelinks information for 862658_KOg

The EuroVoc Classifier on the three text parts “Background Description”, “Technical Description” and “Potential Impact And Applications, result in the following EuroVoc terms related to the KER (Table 2. EuroVoc terms related to KER 862658_KOg):

Table 2. EuroVoc terms related to KER 862658_KOg

fishing industry	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/1372	environmental protection	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2825
conservation of fish stocks	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/133	air quality	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2527
fishing net	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/997	marine pollution	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2535
common fisheries policy	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2455	coastal region	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/3043
fish	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2435	health control	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/192
mollusc	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/1961	sampling	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/623
data collection	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/6030	remote sensing	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/4426
aquaculture	http://eurovoc.europa.eu/2320		

Figure 30 illustrates the semantic network for KER 862658_KOg and its direct neighbours. Relevant target users should address one or more of these topics. Initially, we seek research project participants who share these topics.

Figure 30: The neighbour nodes for "Precision model to map chlorophyll-a concentration in shallow water for the shellfish aquaculture industry." (862658_KOg)

Table 3 indicates that two projects share five EuroVoc terms, 22 projects share four terms, and so on. For these projects we collect the project partners and use the number of shared terms as the ranking criteria (see Table 3 (right)).

Table 3: Projects found for the number of shared EuroVoc terms (left) and the top 10 project partners (right).

#Matches	#Projects
5	2
4	22
3	177
2	1486
1	8759

- 1: [HWU] - HERIOT-WATT UNIVERSITY ['CORDIS:999853400', 'VAT:GB270800579']
- 2: [TALLINN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY] - TALLINNA TEHNIKAÜLIKOOL ['CORDIS:999842536', 'VAT:EE100224841']
- 3: [nan] - RIJKSUNIVERSITEIT GRONINGEN ['CORDIS:999989782', 'VAT:NL001932706B01']
- 4: [HYDRO BOND] - HYDRO BOND ENGINEERING LIMITED ['CORDIS:953174866', 'VAT:GB384575316']
- 5: [ELIKO] - OU ELIKO TEHNOLOGIA ARENDUSKESKUS ['CORDIS:999748058', 'VAT:EE100914193']
- 6: [Aquatera] - AQUATERA LIMITED ['CORDIS:951273375', 'VAT:GB751383825']
- 7: [nan] - THE UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL ['VAT:GB673598875', 'CORDIS:999980567.0']
- 8: [TI] - TEKNOLOGISK INSTITUTT AS ['CORDIS:999418452.0']
- 9: [Bamo] - BAMO IER GMBH ['CORDIS:950504844.0']
- 10: [TRAS] - TELEMARKROYE AS ['CORDIS:950137990.0']

Displaying the paths from project to solution as shown in Figure 31 shows by which EuroVoc terms the project is connected to the solution. When looking at the paths from a stakeholder to the solution, e.g.

from “[HWU] - HERIOT-WATT UNIVERSITY ['CORDIS:999853400', 'VAT:GB270800579]” to the solution 862658_KOg, another options for ranking the stakeholders would be the number of total paths from that stakeholder to that solution. Figure 32 show that the HERIOT-WATT UNIVERSITY participated in a total of 18 projects (blue bubbles), which are linked to the solution by one or more EuroVoc terms (green bubbles).

Using this method, the EuroVoc terms can be ranked according to specific stakeholders. For instance, HWU has been involved in more projects related to “air quality” than to the “fishing industry”.

Figure 31: The path shows how the two projects with 5 shared EuroVoc terms connected to 862658_KOG.

Figure 34: Solution 862658_KOg connected to citizen science engagements.

Rather than utilizing projects as focal points for stakeholder identification, a similar approach can be applied by employing citizen science projects as central hubs. Figure 34 show how 862658_KOg is connected to four citizen science projects sharing four common EuroVoc terms. Here the EuroVoc terms are generated from the description and goals available in the MOE database.

The paths shown illustrate a loose connection between the KO and potential stakeholders, mainly through shared interests in a research or citizen science project. In projects with many participants, not every partner may have worked on the EuroVoc terms matching the KO.

Especially when looking for stakeholders in terms of (end)-users of the KO, a more direct connection is wanted. Figure 35 shows the connection between solution 862658_KOg and the company Norfisk. This company economic activity has been classified by NACE (03.21 Marine aquaculture). The link to the solution is done using an ontology alignment between EuroVoc and NACE.

Ontology alignment, also known as ontology matching, is the process of determining correspondences between concepts in different ontologies. This is a crucial task for enabling interoperability between diverse data sources and systems, allowing them to understand and integrate information seamlessly.

Figure 35: Solution 862658_KOg connected to business company by NACE classification.

For example, let's consider two different classification systems: EuroVoc and NACE. EuroVoc is a multilingual thesaurus covering a wide range of subjects of interest to the European Union, while NACE is the statistical classification of economic activities in the European Union. Ontology alignment between EuroVoc and NACE (Figure 36) would involve identifying that a term like "fishing industry" in EuroVoc corresponds to "03.21 Marine aquaculture" in NACE. This alignment allows data from projects and stakeholders that use different terminologies to be linked and understood in a consistent manner.

Figure 36: Ontology alignment between EuroSciVoc (left) and EuroVoc (right).

Adding this aligned information into the semantic network enables stakeholders to see how different activities and interests connect across various domains, therefore facilitating more comprehensive data analysis and decision-making. Currently the following ontology alignments have been integrated into the semantic network:

- EuroSciVoc <-> EuroVoc (see Figure 36)
- EuroVoc <-> NACE

8 Conclusion

By the end of the PREP4BLUE project, the MOE ontology will have been created and evolved to present a formal representation as a structured framework that defines the relationships and concepts relevant to the Mission Ocean ecosystem domain. It extends the base concepts of the CIDOC-CRM ontology by the concepts related to MO.

Software tools have been created to facilitate the process of mapping data, which involves connecting and relating data points from the MOE database and other sources like projects listed on Ocean Decade or companies from business registers. These tools automate or streamline the process, ensuring efficiency and accuracy.

Using the MOE ontology and data mapping tools, a semantic network has been constructed. A semantic network represents the relationships between different concepts in a way that is understandable for machines. It is currently being used for identifying relevant stakeholders for the knowledge transfer of high potential knowledge/solutions in Task 4.4. A visualization of the semantic network has been integrated in Wavelinks (<https://wavelinks.eu>).

The semantic network serves as the foundation for *Task 4.5 - Pilot tracking of Mission Implementation and tools for assessing progress towards targets*, which involves integrating this network into a final dashboard as a visual interface that provides a user-friendly way to interact with, and interpret the data represented in the semantic network.

Within the task of identifying relevant stakeholders to achieve impact has demonstrated the potential of the semantic network. Beyond finding stakeholders, this network could also be leveraged to identify funding opportunities by linking to open grant proposals using mechanisms akin to those used for stakeholder identification. Another use is identifying laws and regulations for a Key Exploitable Result (KER).

The effectiveness of a semantic network hinges on the quality and accuracy of its data. For example, if the database lacks information on tuna fish farms, the network cannot link or identify them as relevant stakeholders for a KER addressing tuna fish farms. The business registers in EU countries (https://e-justice.europa.eu/106/EN/business_registers_in_eu_countries) would be good source, but the information is only available on a query basis making it exhaustive to “web scrap” the complete dataset. This applies also to funding and regulatory topics by inclusion of funding opportunities at both the EU and national levels, such as utilizing DFG data for Germany.

Maintaining a semantic network requires not only technical expertise but also organizational effort. Regular updates and maintenance are crucial to accommodate changing business contexts, emerging terminologies, and new data sources. Effective management and refinement of the network necessitate skilled personnel such as knowledge engineers and data scientists.

The current Mission Ocean and Waters (MOE) semantic network encompasses 71,928 research projects, 96,863 stakeholders, 10,730 classification terms (including EuroVoc, EuroSciVoc, TRL, NACE), 49 engagement methods, 37 solutions/knowledge outputs, and 2,669,909 relationships between these elements. This foundation establishes a valuable and sustainable knowledge source for the Mission Ocean and Waters initiative for future use.

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